

THE NEED TO FORM THE ACTIVITIES OF TOURIST COMPLEXES IN ORDER TO INCREASE THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE COUNTRY'S TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Annotation. The article analyzes the trends in the development of the tourism industry and determines its place in the country's economy. Factors affecting the competitiveness of competitors and tourist complexes were studied in the tourist market. It was shown that the ability of the country's tourism sector to withstand competition is important in the world's tourist complexes. The importance of tourist complexes for ensuring the competitiveness of the tourism sector was assessed.

Keywords. Tourism industry, tourist complex, tourism sector, competitiveness, tourism competitiveness, tourist zone.

The tourism industry is an important sector of the country's economy, which has a significant impact both on the entire world community and on the economy of a particular region and countries. In some countries, the tourism sector is the main source of foreign exchange earnings and serves to ensure the well-being of the population. At the beginning of the 21st century, international tourism came to the fore, leaving behind the export of cars and oil in terms of its contribution to world exports. According to the World Tourism Organization, in the period before the COVID-19 pandemic, the contribution of the tourism industry in 2019 amounted to 10.3% of world GDP, 7% of world exports, 27.4% of services exports, 9% of capital investments, 11% of consumer spending, more than 5% of tax revenues, the tourism sector played an important role in providing employment for one out of every 11 people.

It should be noted that the tourism industry is one of the sectors most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. The share of tourism in global GDP in 2020 will be 50.4%, or 4.8 trillion dollars. the dollar exchange rate declined to 5.3% compared with a 3.3% reduction in the global economy. During this period, 18.2% of those employed in industry, or 62 million men, were forced to leave work, according to the WTTC, in 2020, tourists' spending on trips within the country decreased by 45%, and the cost of trips abroad decreased by almost 70%. The years 2021-2022 were a period of recovery of international tourism: the volume of production of the tourism industry in 2021 increased by 21.7% compared to 2020 and amounted to 5.8 trillion dollars. the dollar, which

accounted for 6.1% of the world gross product, for comparison, it should be noted that the world gross product grew by 5.8% during this period.

Such growth rates represent an important place for tourism in the global economy and exports, despite the crisis in Pademia. That is why in the current period, the competition between countries, regions, networks and manufacturers is constantly escalating in order to take a worthy place in the international tourism market, to have a high demand for solvency, investment, labor and other resources. In this regard, the concept of competition and competitiveness continues to be one of the main research areas of the international and national tourism industry.

In classical economic theory, the concept of competition is considered as a competition of enterprises for an advantage in the sale of their goods. Later it was argued that the concept of competition would be determined by limited resources and the struggle for buyers' money. The Austrian economist F. von Hayek, describing competition, stated that "competition consists of a mechanism leading to cost reduction, decision-making.

Competitiveness is a comparative category, the reason is expressed in the fact that an economic entity determines the ability to win in a competitive struggle depending on certain characteristics in comparison with other economic entities.

One of the founders of the theory of competitiveness of countries, M. Porter, describing competitiveness, assessed it as "the property of goods, services and market entities to be able to act on an equal footing with similar goods and services on the market." Competitiveness at the national level, says M.Porter, consists in maintaining consistently high labor productivity compared to competitors through the introduction of routine processes for creating inventions and innovations.

When analyzing the issue of competitiveness in tourism, it is necessary to take into account the concepts of competitiveness of tourist complexes, tourist products, and the tourism industry. The competitiveness of tourist complexes is a multifaceted concept, which is determined by external and internal factors and is determined by the attractiveness of the tourist route. The competitiveness of a tourism product is determined by the competitiveness of tourism service providers, that is, the tourism industry. The competitiveness of the tourism sector is determined by the level of economic development of the country, pricing policy, the quality of education and retraining, etc., which determines the level of development of the transport and hotel system, as well as national

competitiveness, depending on the quality of the tourism sector. sectors of the tourism industry.

M. Some of the competitiveness indicators proposed by Porter can also be applied to the tourism sector. A scientifically based approach to the formation and development of the competitiveness of the national economy. According to Porter's concept, the country's competitive advantages include the "National Diamond" of providing labor, materials, knowledge, money, infrastructure resources; the volume, composition and variations in demand for products produced in the country, on domestic and foreign markets; the presence of competitive partner networks includes the structure and strategy of firms.

Considering the conditions of factors, M. Porter considered natural and human resources, scientific potential and information resources in addition to capital, arguing that the factors of competitiveness will be of two types - natural and creative. in his opinion: "national prosperity will not be inherited – it will be created." Applying this point of view to tourism is not always correct, since tourist resources are the determining factor (natural and recreational potential, as well as cultural and historical heritage) of the attractiveness of the most competitive destinations. The state policy on preserving the existing tourism potential is also important.

The conditions of domestic demand are an important, but not decisive factor for the development of a competitive tourism industry in the world market. The formation of a tourist product for foreign tourists is often based on the existing tourist infrastructure created to meet the needs of the population for recreation. There may be a situation in which states initially focus only on attracting the flow of tourists from abroad, and tourism is characterized by a high share of GDP production, exports and employment. At the same time, the factor of attracting capital, rather than domestic demand, becomes more important, the activities of related and auxiliary industries become important, since the economy of such countries will be focused only on the provision of services to the tourism industry and the production of related goods and services.

From the point of view of international tourism, intra-network competition for the production of tourist products also does not matter much when determining the competitiveness of tourist complexes, the reason is that competition between tourist complexes on a global scale is discussed here.

M. Porter in his work believed that direct government intervention in the economy would negatively affect its competitiveness. The supportive role of the

State in relation to tourism should be emphasized. Such support should cover everything from maintaining tourist resources to infrastructure development, facilitating the processing of tourist documents, etc.

Thus, the concept of competitiveness can be considered in relation to a specific element of the tourism industry or as a characteristic of the tourism industry as a whole. In addition, the competitiveness of individual segments of the country's tourism industry also determines its overall level of competitiveness in world markets.

The most important theoretical study of M.Porter's theory is the theory of industrial clusters with pronounced regional aspects, which is based on the following conclusion from the "Diamond of Competitive Advantages": geographically close location of firms operating in a certain network is favorable conditions for creating competitive advantages of regions. A Porter cluster is "a group of joint companies and associated organizations that are geographically adjacent to each other, characterized by the totality of their activities and activities in a particular area."

After a study conducted on clusters of industries, the cluster began to be considered as a key element in various sectors of the economy, as well as in the field of tourism, in particular, a study conducted by the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). In 2010, at the conference on tourism and recreation, the tourist cluster was interpreted as "geographically adjacent companies that form and serve the flow of tourists, use the recreational potential of the area and interact with public organizations and government bodies."

Several studies have been conducted in our country on the development of the tourism sector, improving the competitiveness of the economy of its individual regions, and using a cluster approach to attracting foreign investment in the industry. In particular, B.D.Ollanazarov believes that: "Thanks to the mutual cooperation established in the tourism cluster, conditions will arise for the creation of new products and services, an atmosphere of innovation and business competitiveness. Many tourism clusters are close by themselves, with enterprises of partner industries and supporting clusters, for example, sports and tourist goods - equipment, food, beverages, the media industry will constantly strengthen ties, protecting natural and cultural monuments."

Thus, the tourist complex consists of the sum of business entities, state institutions, public organizations whose activities are located in close proximity to the territory directly or indirectly related to tourism, and the main purpose of their interaction and influence is to develop a high-quality, competitive tourist

product that uses and develops the innovative potential of the territory in which it is located.

In the scientific literature about the essence of the tourist complex , you can see the following points:

- a tourist complex is a system of tourist enterprises, entities providing basic and additional services, acting in cooperation on production, technological and information exchange to create a tourist product;

- a tourist complex is a cluster of companies and institutions engaged in tourism activities in a geographical area. These companies and institutions include suppliers, service providers, government agencies, universities;

- a tourist complex is an area that, in addition to institutions directly related to the tourism sector, includes additional support institutions, transport infrastructure, education and professional retraining systems, consulting and other structures providing services.

Consequently, such characteristics as the fact that tourist complexes have clear territorial boundaries, specialize in the development of a competitive tourist product, the presence of various interactions between the participants of the complex, the presence of supporting networks are characteristic. At the same time, it is necessary to pay special attention to the features of innovation complexes as a structure and their role in ensuring the economic development of the region.

The main purpose of the organization and development of tourist complexes is the development of high-quality, competitive tourist products using the natural, socio-economic resource and innovative potential of the region. Tourist complexes of the regions make it possible to increase the efficiency of the economic entities that make up them. As a result, the opportunities for information exchange and innovation for them will expand, contributing to the coordinated coordination of actions, the joint use of infrastructure facilities serving tourists.

Application of the policy of formation of tourist complexes in the development of tourism, the processes of development of the complex take place in a favorable institutional environment consisting of a set of formal and informal institutions regulating interaction between the subjects of the complex.

Without denying the need for the state to participate in the formation of the tourist complex, it should be emphasized that the main place in the formation and functioning of such structures belongs to economic entities. The readiness of economic entities for integration, effective and open cooperation,

established cooperative ties and the development of informal ties are important in the formation and development of tourist complexes on the territory.

The Institute of Education is a social institution that plays an important role in the formation of a tourist complex, providing qualified personnel to the economic entities located in it. The innovative nature of tourist complexes depends on the activities of research institutes operating in the complex. The introduction of innovations created by research institutes leads to the fact that tourist products become competitive.

It should be noted that in the following years, special attention is paid to the issue of the formation of tourist complexes in our country. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism", adopted on July 18, 2019, defines tourist complexes as follows: "A complex is a tourist complex, as well as independent organizations providing additional services necessary to meet the needs of tourists and guides, as well as a complex of individual entrepreneurs. Tourist complexes form, promote and sell a tourist product in order to provide comprehensive tourist services, increase the competitiveness and quality of tourist activities."

Also on the issue of organizing special tourist zones in the country, including complexes, by creating thematic tourist zones and clusters in the regions of the country in the "Concept of tourism development in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2025", approved by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on additional measures to accelerate the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", taking into account business, etc. The task is to develop new tourist programs.

The analysis of the features inherent in tourist complexes has shown that in many regions of our country there is an opportunity to form tourist complexes. The presence of a system of territorial organizations associated with natural and recreational, historical and cultural resource potential, the active participation of small enterprises in the development of tourist products, the regulation of tourism development is an important factor in the formation of tourist complexes. At the same time, solving this task, it is necessary to create an effective institutional environment for the development of complexes.

It should be noted that the possibilities of an approach to the formation of tourist complexes in the development of tourism in the regions of the republic are still practically not used. Since tourism has unique characteristics, the issue of studying the approach to the development of tourism, to the formation of tourist complexes, its widespread implementation is of particular importance.

The essence of the interaction between the participants of the complex in the tourist complex is that the good work of one of them is a guarantee of the success of the other participants and the mutual collective market. Thus, all companies of the tourist complex benefit from joint activities in the form of a very wide range of opportunities and final total income. Thanks to the mutual cooperation established in the tourist complex, conditions will arise for the creation of new products and services, an atmosphere of innovation and business competition. Many tourist complexes are located next to them, with enterprises of partner industries and auxiliary complexes, for example, with the protection of sports and tourist facilities - equipment, food, beverages, media industry, natural and cultural monuments, constantly strengthening ties.

Ensuring the country's tourism competitiveness, organizing tourist complexes using its natural and recreational potential and historical and cultural resources provides the following opportunities:

- coordination of joint actions of tourism business, science and state management organizations;
- to increase the efficiency of the activities of the participants of the tourist complex by reducing costs, including transaction costs, by expanding access to resources (information, innovations and technologies) and sharing infrastructure facilities;
- accelerate the process of creating and launching innovative products on the market by strengthening the interaction between producers and consumers of tourist services;
- formation of a favorable investment climate in the region due to the availability of benefits for investors involved in the formation of the complex;
- stimulating competition by improving the conditions for the creation and development of a new business;
- the formation of a closed chain of value-added growth as a result of the accumulation of all the necessary links in the supply of a tourist product to consumers in one area.

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